

A STUDY ON DR APJ ABDULKALAM'S VISION FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

by

B.SANKAR

Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of History
C.Abdul Hakeem College Mel Visharam
Affiliated to Thiruvallur University,
Serkkadu, Vellore

and

Dr.H.K.SULAIMAN KHAN

Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of History
C.Abdul Hakeem College Mel Visharam
Affiliated to Thiruvallur University,
Serkkadu, Vellore

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Abstract

In India Dr APJ Abdulkalam's actions and writings envisioned the idea of, nationhood is a feeling of pride and a sense of achievement towards one's nation. He is simple and humble conduct of the President of the country laid a moral code of ethics and principles not only for the common man but also the leaders positioned at the helm of affairs. His scientific achievements brought glory to the nation. its economic advancement. By this India would attain its lost glory and this would bring about the renaissance in the nation. Kalam thus considered the economic progress essential for evolving nationhood. He stated that scientific and technological accomplishments for the nation. It is the big brother stage of the nation where there is revival of culture, values and traditions. He assigned important role to the family and society of the individual.

Introduction

In the Indian political scenario witnessed Presidents getting elected purely on political considerations compromising the high standards of the highest office. In this era of dilution the society especially the youth desperately needed a role model for imbibing in them a passion of national spirit. In the background of disappointment and despair when corruption, immorality and low value took the centre stage which subsequently got reflected in disenchantment, dissatisfaction, disillusionment, agitations and unrest among the youth, the rules were seen taking

the system for a ride. In such a situation of hopelessness during the regime of Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee, India on 25th July 2002 welcomed its eleventh President whose contribution in science and technology was not only path breaking but he also was a great literary figure who composed fine masterpieces on social, cultural, political and economic subjects. His books, writings, poems, and literary works portray nationhood striking the delicate chord of patriotism among the countrymen especially the youth who passionately looked for a role model. Kalam strengthened his idea of nationhood in Ignited Minds. His vision 2020 was aimed at economic progress of the nation. Kalam's books were directed towards social awakening and spiritual enlightenment of the citizens of the country especially the youth, to arouse a sentiment of loyalty towards the nation.

Kalam Era

Most of the Presidents in India have played a positive role in nation-building, but Kalam was the person who entered the Indian political scene with a vision of transformation of the nation. His concern for the nation is deeply reflected in his writings. His intellect was a rare combination of a poet and a politician, the scientist and the mystic, idealist and the realist. Kalam was a born visionary, and it was this vision of his which instilled a writer in him. His ideology is reflected in the words of S.M.Khan: What has impressed me the most is Dr Kalam's vision to make India a great power. I remember his keynote address delivered at the 117th anniversary of The Tribune, on 22 February 1988. He said: "Fifty years after accomplishing the first vision of freedom, the nation must have a second vision. We must dream of living in a developed country. We are an underdeveloped or a developing nation. A developing nation means a weaker economy. And as a nation, it does not have a standing in the international forums. It is a time to forget all our previous problems and strive to be a developed nation. All of us must visualize India as a big nation -a nation with nearly one billion people. Imagine a small India with about one billion people. When you are big, you must think big.

APJ Abdul Kalam graced the Indian Presidency from 2002 to 2007, becoming the 11th President of the country during the NDA government. The Head of the State at that time was seen to be the titular head that drew attention to himself and his office only when somber constitutional questions were thrown up after an uncertain electoral verdict particularly the hung Lok Sabha. For the rest of the time, President of India was to be wrapped and enclosed in dignified and ceremonial hauteur, acting on the aid and advice of an elected government collectively responsible to the Lok Sabha.

Kalam's Vision

DR APJ ABDULKalam's was quite positive about the nation's growth and development, he also talked about the challenge faced by the nations. He stated that the challenges were diverse and yet they were generally applicable and common for all nations. They would require co-operation across borders. Technologies and complexities and cost factors in solving issues like water, energy, independence, environment protection and health would require intense co-operation in research development and operationalization. For this we need to work together to understand and protect against the fury of nature like earthquakes, floods, cyclones and famines etc. Kalam talked about the need for a resilient economy. He said that lessons should be learnt from the various economic turbulences. The youth should be prepared to face such challenges. They should be enabled with global cadre skills, sets and higher education skills. Only then they would be able to contribute to national development.

Kalam's vision of a developed status for India was an endless pursuit. He stated that even after the attainment of a developed status by 2020, it does not mean that we can rest on our laurels. It was a long term vision and only the people with ignited minds and embodied knowledge and skill would be ready for such a vision. This vision should then become a part of the nation and the transcending governments of the present as well as the future. Once India becomes developed, it

should be able to take care of its strategic interests and abilities. For this it will need the strength of its healthy, educated and prosperous people, the strength of its economy as well as the strength to protect its strategic interests. Putting his views on the vision of national scrutiny, Kalam wrote,

In his book, *India 2020: A Vision for the New Millenium*, Dr Kalam identified the core competencies of India which are a pre requisite for its development. His prime concern was upliftment of the people of the country. For this the country needs to eradicate the poverty of its men, it should provide health for all, and efforts should be made to provide good education and skills for all the youth and and also they should have ample employment opportunities. The country should be a net exporter as its exports should supercede its imports. Insecurity also it should be self reliant and thus it should build up, sustain and improve all these qualities in future. These can only be realized only when the country identifies its core competencies.

Economic Development

According to Kalam, India's first vision was set by the glorious generation of the freedom fighters who had a vision of free India and laid down their lives for this cause. After the attainment of political freedom, the next generation set the second vision for India. They made whole hearted efforts to put India on the path of economic, agricultural and technological development. Kalam was positive that India would definitely acquire the status of a developed country by 2020. He interpreted the term 'developed nation' in terms of common man. It meant the major transformation of our national economy in such a way that it became one of the largest economies in the world. A developed nation would be one where the countrymen lived above the poverty line and their education and health was of high standard. The national security would be reasonably assured in a developed nation and the core competence in certain areas needed to be enhanced

so that the production of quality goods is increased thereby bringing all round prosperity for the countrymen.

Human Resource

Kalam asserted that India's human resource was one of its greatest core competencies. In his 'Technology Vision Document', he advocated the formation of a human resource cadre that would form the formation of the action packages for the country. Such a cadre would lead to economic achievement of the nation. Our past experience has also shown that technological and industrial achievements of our country have resulted due to the persistence effort of thousands of young men and women who have studied in ordinary schools and colleges. Very few out of them are products of prestigious institutes like IITs etc. people in various professions such as doctors, engineers, technicians, nurses, artistes, writers, journalists, clerks, teachers, accountants, various kinds of professionals and other in the work-force and even the people working in the software are generally those who cannot even speak English fluently but have achieved mastery and perfection in their profession. So Kalam staunchly believed in the power of the people who are actually the nation's asset for economic progress.

Natural Resource

India's natural resource base is also core strength of the country. Though India does not have rich deposits of all the ores and minerals but it has abundant supplies of most of them especially good ores of aluminium and steel. India is also rich in wonder metal titanium and other rare earth materials. Besides these, India has an excellent base for living resource, biodiversity, abundant sunshine, varied agro-climatic conditions. These conditions vary from arctic cold to tropical green to bare deserts and thus provide a great diversity to our motherland.

What is required is to tap its potential to the fullest. Thus Kalam dreamt of an India whose 'Technology Vision 2020' was built around its natural base, its vast human resource base and the core competencies of the nation.

Kalam considered the economic security of the nation and people of utmost importance as it leads to the prosperity of the people and their continued health and being. Kalam identified various parameters of economic prosperity. He dreamt of an India which would prosper and develop economically by 2020. The Presidential post was accepted by him with a view to implement his 'Vision 2020 Document'. Keeping in mind India's needs, core strengths and competencies, the focus was to develop crucial sectors. They were agro- food processing, road transportation, civil aviation waterways, electric power telecommunications, advanced sensors, engineering industries, electronics and communications, materials and processing, chemical processing industries, life sciences and biotechnology, health care strategic industries and services.

Basic Needs

The first and foremost step required in this direction according to Kalam was acquiring self sufficiency in food and agriculture sector. As it is a well known fact that about forty percent of the people in our country live below the poverty line. The situation is much better than what it was before independence and even during the 1960s. At that time we were dependent on America for our requirement of wheat. But this crisis gave the country's leadership an opportunity to make efforts to become self sufficient in food grains in the 1970s. India took the advantages of these technologies, experimented with them and it led to the food grain self sufficiency. With this the programmers of the Vision 2020 became confident that India would emerge as a global power in terms of agricultural produce and would become capable of meeting the global standards.

Challenges of Agriculture

Certain challenges to agriculture were too identified in the vision document. There was a big problem for agriculture in the areas having rain fed agriculture. For this, efforts were made to connect different systems and water bodies with canals for the improvement of agriculture. Application of bio-technology was a positive step to obtain better quality yield for crops. There were a number of improvements in the agricultural implements, machinery, technologies, agro-chemicals and fertilizers which contributed a great deal for the improvement. Achieving these projects would be possible by the actions taken to realize them. For this it was necessary to take the farmers and people into confidence and reaching the benefits of technology to them. The vision should not be considered just a project report or a plan target. It should be considered as an articulation to obtain the desired result.

Besides, the development of the agro food processing and agricultural products coming from biological resources, there are non living natural resources which add to the economic wealth of the nation. They include energy giving resources such as petroleum and natural gas and chemicals for daily use such as salt etc. they also incorporate metallic products which occur inside the earth in the form of ores. A country's social and economic growth is closely linked to the proficiency with which people have been able to use and shape these materials. Dr Kalam recognized the efficiency of these materials which have become the bedrock of a country's development. Light weight, high performance materials and alloys have helped in building aircrafts, satellites, launch vehicles and missiles. Our houses are full of modern materials such as stainless steel vessels, non-sticking pans, plastic and fibre glass products. Various machines, audio visual equipments, musical instruments and innumerable articles depend crucially on such materials. These materials have penetrated every sphere of modern life.

According to Kalam, the development pattern of chemical product industry could be divided into three phase: penetration, consolidation and speciality. In the penetration phase, the chemical products which protect the crops and improve health and thus contribute to economic and social advancement were taken up. In the consolidation phase, resource rich countries geared up to meet domestic demands as well as exports. In the specialization phase, emphasis was placed on the manufacture and marketing of speciality chemicals. Dr Kalam emphasized the study of traditional knowledge. Earlier advocates of the scientific approach scorned the skills and knowledge of the ancient societies on the ground that they were not rational or empirically proven. But later, many thinkers, scientists and technologists revisited ancient knowledge bases. Large amounts of on traditional systems of medicine, the use of herbs and even metallurgy was gathered and applied to the modern knowledge. We are aware of many foreign companies which are funding academics from Indian Universities to record such ancient knowledge. These companies pay them handsomely to recover the knowledge from them. Kalam wanted that such knowledge should be retained in the country and we should attempt global leadership in the production of such commodities.

Service sector

Service sector is an important linkage of the 'Vision 2020 Document'. The service sector has come to be considered a major part of the economy. This sector includes anything other than direct agriculture or manufacturing. Kalam classified the various parts of the service sector as tourism, testing and calibration, technical and management consultancy, training security services, banking, financial services, real estates, marketing, media and advertising etc. but Kalam reiterated that India would not be able to build its future on service sector alone. Though service sector was a major component of the economy, but India could not ignore the agricultural and the manufacturing sector. If the service sector was properly developed along with the other two basis sectors only then it would give rise to various opportunities and thus find new jobs and individual prosperity.

Kalam gave due place to the service sector in his "Technology Vision 2020 Document", as it covered multiple sectors of technology and manufacture. Kalam stated that in this regard, in a country of one billion, Indians should gear themselves to take up the opportunities offered by the service sector in their march towards an India where the Indians would possess wealth and well-being. Kalam recognized the importance of health care for all and stated that any society would be judged by its ability to provide universal health care for its people. This does not mean just to treat diseases and ailments but also to prevent their onset by means of suitable systems and measures.

The non-communicable diseases can be treated through regular medication and precautionary measures. Most communicable diseases can be prevented by suitable sanitation system, control of disease spreading materials and immunization programmes. Nutrition and dietary supplements were required to control various diseases. Hygiene is also quite essential in this respect. Proper drainage of dirty water, disposal of garbage, sewage and human and industrial waste, was crucial for a clean micro- environment and was a pre-requisite of preventive health care. Preventive health care systems like inoculation, vaccination and immunization and periodic checks were the next in this step. Kalam's main concern in his Vision Document was that health for all Indians would be realized before 2020.

The significance of all the linkages of development become noteworthy if there is absence of enabling structure. The world today has become accessible and connected in a complicated way, thanks to the technology of transportation and telecommunication. A modern development economy cannot be built if it is cut off from the rest of the manufacturing and business centre. Dr Kalam in his Vision Document, asserted the mythical significance of the rivers. He emphasized that the water of the rivers should be conserved and recycled. He considered the river waterways as the most energy efficient transport system. Kalam laid the concept of 'smart waterways' which have sufficient navigable depth

and width so that the vessels were able to navigate them throughout the year. Thus networking of rivers is absolutely essential. This would not only provide new water routes but also help distribute water from areas of excess to those that are deficient. A nation would march towards developing country status if it evolves an efficient water management policy. Besides the conventional forms of infrastructure, Kalam advocated the importance of modern infrastructure and telecommunication which is crucial to any competitive economy. The emergence of digital technology and information technology has opened new avenues for our country. These services should be available to a maximum number of subscribers. For this Kalam added a few assertions in the vision document. It was thus necessary to increase the number of lines to increase the proportion of digital lines, use digital switching technologies and increasing the capacity of the access and transmission network.

A glimpse into his work reveals that he laid emphasis on all the aspects of a nation. He anchored as the chief architect of India's Mission technology and his role in making significant advances in the space technology is incomparable. On the other hand he gives immense importance to the birds, animals and flowers and even an 'Arjun Tree' which according to him is the nation's wealth. He considered the people and the youth as the nation and their 'Ignited minds as the biggest power of the nation and hence his writings reflect the betterment, enhancement and development of their lives. He always stood for a vision to transform the nation with advances in technology, agriculture and military power. He had a vision for India i.e by 2020 India would become a nation which will be a super power globally. He believed that a United Vision launched with new vigor would bring the young force into action and ignite their young minds. This would involve them in the task of nation building.

Conclusion

Resulted from this vision, according to Kalam is to transform India into a self-sufficient and developed nation by its economic advancement. By this India would attain its lost glory and this would bring about the renaissance in the nation. Kalam thus considered the economic progress essential for evolving nationhood. This aspect of nationhood is mentioned in his books *India 2020: A Vision for the New Millennium* and *We Can Do It: Thought for Change*. Scientific and Technological Vision: Kalam's third vision for the nation is the attainment of scientific and technological advancement. After the nation has acquired economic achievement, it finds ways to demonstrate its superiority over others. Perhaps through conquests and also excellency in various fields. It also enters into competition with powerful nations of the world and this stage Kalam referred as the warrior stage. Kalam in his books *Wings of Fire* and *Re-Ignited*, discussed the nation's accomplishments in this field. Social Vision: Kalam stated that after scientific and technological accomplishments, the next vision for the nation is Social vision. It is the big brother stage of the nation where there is revival of culture, values and traditions. He assigned important role to the family and society of the individual.

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